

Supplementary information

High-risk contaminants detected in wastewater effluent samples can be prioritized prior to structural assignment using machine learning tools

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Table of contents

Text S1. LC-HRMS instrumental parameters

Text S2. Data processing

Table S1. Mixture of contaminants (159) and metadata (**excel**)

Table S2. Surface water suspect (SWS) list (**excel**)

Table S3. MS-DIAL processing parameters

Table S4. SIRIUS command

Table S5. GNPS parameters

Table S6. GNPS libraries

Table S7. MetFrag parameters

Table S8. Processing steps yields

Table S9. Comparison of rank one candidate structure vs fingerprint-based priority score

Table S10. WWTP1 samples overview

Table S11. WWTP2 samples overview

Table S12. WWTP3 samples overview

Table S13. All features $PS_{\text{precautionary}}$ in three WWTP samples and the library matches from GNPS (**excel**)

Table S14. $PS_{\text{precautionary}}$ features of WWTP2 with library match and categorization (**excel**)

Table S15. Summary of high-risk features in WWTP2 effluent.

Table S16. Candidates suggested by SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID for features $>PS_{RQ=1}$ in all WWTP effluents (**excel**)

Table S17. Candidates suggested by MetFrag for features $>PS_{RQ=1}$ in all WWTP effluents (**excel**)

Table S18. Standards used for level 1 confirmation in WWTP3

Figure S1. Barplot summary of the processing for spiked contaminants in influent, effluent and solvent

Figure S2. Chemical-specific identification summary

Figure S3. Correlation of structure-based priority scores for all samples

Figure S4. Priority score correlations for any candidates vs no candidates

Figure S5. SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID score distribution for in rank one incorrect structure, and correct structure independent of the rank

Figure S6. Area, LC_{50} , and IE contribution to PS

Figure S7. Risk quotient comparison with predicted fingerprint-based priority score using $PS_{\text{precautionary}}$

Figure S8. Overview of WWTP1 processing results

Figure S9. Overview of WWTP3 processing results

Figure S10. The fingerprint-based and library-matched candidate structures priority score correlation for wastewater features with $PS > PS_{RQ=1}$

Figure S11. Standards and detected features plotted on U-MAP fitted on PubChemLite (PCL) chemicals

References

Text S1. LC-HRMS instrumental parameters

The aqueous mobile phase contained 10 mM acetic acid, and 10 mM acetic acid in methanol was used as the organic mobile phase. For reversed-phase separation, the organic mobile phase composition increased linearly from 5% to 95% over 10 min, was held constant for 2 min, decreased back to 5% in 0.1 min and kept at 5% for 2.9 min for equilibration. The mobile phase flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the column temperature was held at 40 °C. The autosampler temperature was held at 5 °C, and an injection volume of 100 µL was used for all samples.

All samples were analyzed in positive electrospray ionization (ESI) mode using a Q Exactive Orbitrap HRMS (Thermo Fischer Scientific). The spray voltage was 3500 V, the capillary temperature was 320°C and the probe heater temperature was 350 °C. The max spray current was 100 µA and the S-lens RF level was 55%. The gas parameters were the following: sheath gas was 50 arbitrary units (AU), aux gas was 13 AU and spare gas was 3 AU. Full scan measurements were performed in triplicate from 100 – 1500 m/z with a nominal mass resolution of 120,000. All DDA and DIA acquisition conditions were performed in duplicate, and with the same instrumental settings as the full scan, with the exception of lower resolution (15,000 nominal), and the normalised collision energy was always 30.

Text S2. Data processing

All full scans of influent and effluent samples from the same WWTP, both spiked and unspiked, were processed together with MS-DIAL for feature alignment and signal integration. For all features detected in full scan, the average signal in samples had to exceed the average signal in solvent blanks by a factor of three. Correction of signal drift was done by normalizing all peak areas with the peak area of imazalil-d5 internal standard, which was most reproducibly detected. All MS^1 peak areas for spiked chemicals and features over $PS_{RQ=1}$ in the wastewater were manually examined and the integration was corrected if necessary.

All features detected in full scan measurements were categorized into removable chemicals ($area_{influent}/area_{effluent} \geq 5$), transformation products ($area_{effluent}/area_{influent} \geq 5$) and persistent chemicals ($5 > area_{influent}/area_{effluent} > 0.2$) based on effluent to influent peak area ratio. The presence of standards in wastewater samples was evaluated based on retention time (<0.2 min) and precursor ion m/z (<10 ppm) matching. Additional confirmation based on fragmentation spectra was hampered by the lack of MS^2 spectra which were only triggered for 38% of the features potentially corresponding to standards.

In order to evaluate fragmentation information separately for each sample, the MS^2 measurements of each sample together with solvent blanks were processed independently for each data acquisition method in MS-DIAL. The alignment files were further processed in R to generate the .ms files of each feature with MS^2 , and process these with SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID^{1,2} for probabilistic fingerprint prediction and tentative identification.

The toxicity and ionization efficiency were predicted for all features which yielded probabilistic fingerprints from MS^2 spectra using SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID. The probabilistic fingerprints corresponding to the highest ranked molecular formula were used as input to *MS2Tox* and *MS2Quant* models. For the latter, eluent descriptors, such as pH of the aqueous phase, surface tension, viscosity, and presence of ammonium-based additive, were calculated based on the retention time of the feature and LC gradient. *MS2Tox* and *MS2Quant* were retrained on structural fingerprints calculated with the *fingerprinter* function from SIRIUS to ensure compatibility and are available from https://github.com/kruvelab/MS2Quant/tree/main/development/WW_prioritization_models.

Table S3. MS-DIAL (version 4.80) analysis parameters for data processing adapted from Peets et al.³

Data Collection tab		
Mass accuracy (centroid parameter)		
MS1 tolerance:	0.001 Da	Da
MS2 tolerance:	0.003 Da	Da
Data collection parameters		
Retention time begin:	1	min
Retention time end:	13	min
MS1 mass range begin:	100	Da
MS1 mass range end:	1500	Da
MS/MS mass range begin:	50	Da
MS/MS mass range end:	1500	Da
Isotope recognition		
Maximum charged number:	2	
Consider Cl and Br elements:	Yes (checked)	
Execute retention time corrections:	No (unchecked)	
Peak detection tab		
Peak detection parameters		
Minimum peak height:	10000	amplitude
Mass slice width:	0.1	Da
Smoothing method:	Linear weighted moving average	
Smoothing level:	3	scan
Minimum peak width:	5	scan
MS2Dec tab		
Deconvolution parameters		
Sigma window value:	1	
MS/MS abundance cut off:	0	amplitude
Exclude after precursor ion:	Yes (checked)	
Keep the isotopic ions until:	0.5	Da
Keep the isotopic ions w/o MS2Dec:	Yes (checked)	
Adduct tab		
Adduct ion setting		
[M+H] ⁺	Included (checked)	
[M+NH ₄] ⁺		
[M+Na] ⁺		
Alignment tab		
Alignment parameters setting		
Retention time tolerance:	0.1	min
MS1 tolerance:	0.003	Da
Retention time factor:	0.5	
MS1 factor:	0.5	
Peak count filter:	0	%
N% detected in at least one group:	100	%
Remove features based on blank information:	Yes (checked)	
Sample max / blank average:	5	Fold change
Keep removable features and assign the tag:	Yes (checked)	
Gap filling by compulsion:	Yes (checked)	

Table S4. SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID (version 5.8.3) was run over command line interface; command was run using the following parameters:

"sirius -i <folder_with_ms_files> -o <SIRIUS_results_output_directory> formula -p orbitrap -ppm-max 5 -ppm-max-ms2 10 -E CH -e ONP[8]B[11]Si[9]S[12]Cl[18]Se[2]Br[10]F[6]K[1]Na[1]As[2] -d All fingerprint structure write-summaries"	The whole command used for running SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID
sirius	Using SIRIUS command line tool
-i <folder_with_ms_files>	Folder with .ms files used as input to SIRIUS
-o <SIRIUS_results_output_directory>	Folder where SIRIUS results will be saved out
formula	Formula predictions
-p orbitrap	Mass-spectrometer used to acquire data
-ppm-max 5	Maximum allowed mass deviation (parts per million) for MS ¹ data
-ppm-max-ms2 10	Maximum allowed mass deviation (parts per million) for MS ² data
-E CH	Elements that must be contained in the predicted formula; without upper limit
-e ONP[8]B[11]Si[9]S[12]Cl[18]Se[2]Br[10]F[6]K[1]Na[1]As[2]	Elements that are allowed in formula prediction. Upper limits are defined for some elements by using square brackets with the upper limit count after the element.
-d All fingerprint structure	All databases listed in SIRIUS were used for formula validation and structure suggestions.
write-summaries	Create and save the SIRIUS summary files.

Table S5. Library matching parameters used in GNPS.⁴ Library matches were later additionally filtered based on cosine score ≥ 0.7 and matching peaks ≥ 3 values.

MOLECULAR-LIBRARYSEARCH-V2 (Workflow version release_28)		
Search Options		
Precursor Ion Mass Tolerance:	0.025	Da
Min Matched Peaks:	3	
Fragment Ion Mass Tolerance:	0.02	Da
Score Threshold:	0.6	
Advanced Search Options (defaults)		
Library Class:	Bronze	
Top Hits Per Spectrum:	1	
Spectral Library:	speclibs	
Search Analogs:	Don't Search	
Maximum Analog Search Mass Difference:	100.0	
Advanced Filtering Options (defaults)		
Filter StdDev Intensity:	0.0	
Filter Precursor Window:	Filter	
Filter peaks in 50Da Window:	Filter	
Filter SNR Intensity:	0.0	
Filter Library:	Filter Library	
Min Peak Int:	0.0	

Table S6. Libraries used for matching. The library matching was performed using Global Natural Products Social Molecular Networking (GNPS) with all available libraries (queried 2024-12-09 to 2025-01-07).

speclibs/GNPS-SAM-SIK-KANG-LEGACY-LIBRARY/GNPS-SAM-SIK-KANG-LEGACY-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/CASMI/CASMI.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-SCIEX-LIBRARY/GNPS-SCIEX-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/MONA/MONA.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-CLINICALCOLLECTION2/GNPS-NIH-CLINICALCOLLECTION2.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-SELLECKCHEM-FDA-PART1/GNPS-SELLECKCHEM-FDA-PART1.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-PESTICIDES-NEGATIVE/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-PESTICIDES-NEGATIVE.mgf
speclibs/LDB_POSITIVE/LDB_POSITIVE.mgf
speclibs/BIRMINGHAM-UHPLC-MS-NEG/BIRMINGHAM-UHPLC-MS-NEG.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-CLINICALCOLLECTION1/GNPS-NIH-CLINICALCOLLECTION1.mgf
speclibs/BERKELEY-LAB/BERKELEY-LAB.mgf
speclibs/MMV_POSITIVE/MMV_POSITIVE.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY_ROUND2_NEGATIVE/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY_ROUND2_NEGATIVE.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-SELLECKCHEM-FDA-PART2/GNPS-SELLECKCHEM-FDA-PART2.mgf
speclibs/LEAFBOT/LEAFBOT.mgf
speclibs/PNNL-LIPIDS/PNNL-LIPIDS-NEGATIVE.mgf
speclibs/PNNL-LIPIDS/PNNL-LIPIDS-POSITIVE.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIST14-MATCHES/GNPS-NIST14-MATCHES.mgf
speclibs/DRUGS-OF-ABUSE-LIBRARY/DRUGS-OF-ABUSE-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/IQAMDB/IQAMDB.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-D2-AMINO-LIPID-LIBRARY/GNPS-D2-AMINO-LIPID-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-IOBA-NHC/GNPS-IOBA-NHC.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-SMALLMOLECULEPHARMACOLOGICALLYACTIVE/GNPS-NIH-SMALLMOLECULEPHARMACOLOGICALLYACTIVE.mgf
speclibs/BILELIB19/BILELIB19.mgf
speclibs/HCE-CELL-LYSATE-LIPIDS/HCE-CELL-LYSATE-LIPIDS.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-EMBL-MCF/GNPS-EMBL-MCF.mgf
speclibs/XANTHONES-DB/XANTHONES-DB.mgf
speclibs/TUEBINGEN-NATURAL-PRODUCT-COLLECTION/TUEBINGEN-NATURAL-PRODUCT-COLLECTION.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-PRESTWICKPHYTOCHEM/GNPS-PRESTWICKPHYTOCHEM.mgf
speclibs/MIADB/MIADB.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-PESTICIDES-POSITIVE/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-PESTICIDES-POSITIVE.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-MSMLS/GNPS-MSMLS.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-FAULKNERLEGACY/GNPS-FAULKNERLEGACY.mgf
speclibs/MASSBANKEU/MASSBANKEU.mgf
speclibs/LDB_NEGATIVE/LDB_NEGATIVE.mgf
speclibs/HMDB/HMDB.mgf
speclibs/BIRMINGHAM-UHPLC-MS-POS/BIRMINGHAM-UHPLC-MS-POS.mgf
speclibs/DERPLICATOR_IDENTIFIED_LIBRARY/DERPLICATOR_IDENTIFIED_LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/ECG-ACYL-AMIDES-C4-C24-LIBRARY/ECG-ACYL-AMIDES-C4-C24-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/ECG-ACYL-ESTERS-C4-C24-LIBRARY/ECG-ACYL-ESTERS-C4-C24-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/PSU-MSMLS/PSU-MSMLS.mgf
speclibs/BMDMS-NP/BMDMS-NP.mgf
speclibs/RESPECT/RESPECT.mgf
speclibs/SUMNER/SUMNER.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-LIBRARY/GNPS-LIBRARY.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-MISC/GNPS-COLLECTIONS-MISC.mgf
speclibs/MMV_NEGATIVE/MMV_NEGATIVE.mgf
speclibs/NEO-MSMS/NEO-MSMS.mgf
speclibs/UM-NPDC/UM-NPDC.mgf
speclibs/MASSBANK/MASSBANK.mgf
speclibs/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY_ROUND2_POSITIVE/GNPS-NIH-NATURALPRODUCTSLIBRARY_ROUND2_POSITIVE.mgf

Table S7. MetFrag^{5,6} (version 2.6.1) was run over command line interface using the following parameters. Ten candidates, ranked highest based on overall score calculated by MetFrag, were selected for predicted priority score comparison (FP-based PS vs candidate structure-based PS).

MetFragDatabaseType	PubChem
NeutralPrecursorMass	[detected m/z] - 1.00727
DatabaseSearchRelativeMassDeviation	5
FragmentPeakMatchAbsoluteMassDeviation	0.001
FragmentPeakMatchRelativeMassDeviation	5
PrecursorIonMode	1
IsPositiveIonMode	True
MetFragScoreTypes	FragmenterScore
MetFragScoreWeights	1.0
MetFragCandidateWriter	CSV
MaximumTreeDepth	2
MetFragPreProcessingCandidateFilter	UnconnectedCompoundFilter
MetFragPostProcessingCandidateFilter	InChIKeyFilter

Figure S1. Barplot of the number of chemicals that can be potentially seen, MS² was acquired, fingerprints (FP) were predicted, correct formula was suggested for the predicted fingerprint, and the correct structure was suggested within all candidate structures independent of the rank (any) or as rank one structure. Counts are shown for solvent, influent (INF), and effluent (EFF) samples at three concentration levels of the spiked mixture of contaminants, and in three acquisition modes (Top5, SWS, DIA). The green bars and numbers correspond to spiked chemicals not present in the unspiked wastewater sample while grey bars and numbers additionally include spiked chemicals that were present in wastewater sample prior to spiking.

Table S8. Processing steps yields (counts) for potentially seen chemicals, triggered MS² spectra, features with predicted fingerprint information, correct formula was suggested for the predicted fingerprint, correct structure found within the candidate structures independent of the rank, and rank one correct structure. The counts are provided for spiked chemicals that were not detected in unspiked wastewater samples, while the numbers in the brackets correspond to all spiked chemicals including chemicals potentially present in the unspiked wastewater samples.

method	Concentration level	sample	Potentially seen chemicals	MS ² spectrum triggered	Fingerprint information	Fingerprint-based formula match	Correct structure - any rank	Correct structure - rank one
Top5	50 µg/L	solvent	90 (90)	86 (86)	75 (75)	50 (50)	64 (64)	53 (53)
Top5	50 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	47 (86)	42 (72)	26 (49)	32 (60)	29 (50)
Top5	5 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	43 (82)	39 (70)	20 (41)	28 (57)	23 (45)
Top5	0.5 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	31 (63)	28 (57)	20 (41)	24 (49)	19 (37)
Top5	50 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	58 (87)	48 (74)	32 (49)	41 (63)	37 (53)
Top5	5 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	55 (84)	47 (72)	31 (51)	39 (61)	34 (50)
Top5	0.5 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	47 (72)	38 (62)	20 (38)	31 (53)	27 (43)
SWS	50 µg/L	solvent	28 (28)	24 (24)	21 (21)	15 (15)	17 (17)	15 (15)
SWS	50 µg/L	IN	12 (28)	10 (23)	10 (23)	7 (17)	8 (20)	8 (18)
SWS	5 µg/L	IN	12 (28)	10 (24)	9 (23)	4 (17)	8 (21)	7 (16)
SWS	0.5 µg/L	IN	12 (28)	9 (22)	9 (22)	3 (15)	5 (18)	5 (15)
SWS	50 µg/L	EF	16 (28)	13 (24)	12 (21)	9 (14)	10 (18)	10 (17)
SWS	5 µg/L	EF	16 (28)	13 (24)	13 (24)	10 (20)	11 (21)	10 (17)
SWS	0.5 µg/L	EF	16 (28)	11 (21)	9 (19)	5 (13)	9 (19)	7 (15)
DIA	50 µg/L	solvent	90 (90)	87 (87)	63 (63)	21 (21)	41 (41)	27 (27)
DIA	50 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	46 (88)	40 (71)	14 (24)	24 (47)	16 (26)
DIA	5 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	43 (82)	35 (67)	9 (20)	17 (37)	9 (16)
DIA	0.5 µg/L	IN	47 (90)	36 (70)	28 (56)	3 (12)	14 (31)	7 (12)
DIA	50 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	58 (87)	48 (72)	18 (33)	28 (47)	17 (26)
DIA	5 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	55 (83)	46 (72)	15 (26)	27 (47)	17 (26)
DIA	0.5 µg/L	EF	59 (90)	53 (78)	42 (65)	14 (22)	25 (43)	9 (14)

Figure S2. Chemical-specific identification summary with SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID over seven samples: standard mix as well as influent and effluent samples spiked on three concentration levels. Chemical-specific analysis reveals that some chemicals have very low identification rates by SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID. For example, the highly ecotoxic chemical pyridaben (LC_{50} Rainbow trout 1.1-3.1 ug/l in 96 h study)^{7,8} yielded SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID fingerprints in all seven samples with Top5 and DIA methods (m/z not present in SWS inclusion list); however, the structure was never correctly identified. Similarly, for theophylline, a caffeine metabolite, the correct structure was ranked between second and fifth candidate structure.

Figure S3. Correlation of priority scores calculated based on SMILES and predicted fingerprints. Fingerprints were predicted based on MS² spectra triggered by Top5, SWS, or DIA data acquisition method for standards in pure solvent and standards spiked in three concentration levels to wastewater influent as well as effluent. Approximately half of the spiked chemicals were also present in the influent and effluent samples, which means that the area and therefore priority score for these chemicals are elevated; however, the priority score calculated from the structure as well as from fingerprints that rely on the same area and can still be compared. The priority scores were compared based on number of detected chemicals (N), root mean squared error (RMSE) and squared Pearson correlation coefficient (R²). Number of detected chemicals (N),

Figure S4. Priority score calculated based on predicted fingerprints vs correct SMILES-based for the 90 chemicals in influent and effluent samples spiked at three concentration levels. The features are categorized based on if they yielded any candidate structures or no candidate structures using SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID.

Table S9. The p-values from Wilcoxon signed rank test for differences in priority score calculated based on predicted fingerprints or based on rank one suggested structure. The correct SMILES-based predicted priority score was used as basis (ground truth).

method	Rank category	count	RMSE FP	RMSE rank one SMILES	R^2 FP	R^2 rank one SMILES	p-value
Top5	rank = 1	276	0.492	2.60×10^{-16}	0.817	1	1.55×10^{-56}
Top5	rank = 2-5	54	0.604	0.613	0.785	0.772	0.649
Top5	rank > 5	12	0.462	0.405	0.903	0.947	0.887
Top5	incorrect	22	1.330	1.22	0.490	0.464	0.698
Top5	no identification	43	0.691	NA	0.717	NA	NA
SWS	rank = 1	98	0.582	1.98×10^{-16}	0.708	1	9.17×10^{-18}
SWS	rank = 2-5	19	0.604	0.844	0.692	0.533	0.588
SWS	incorrect	4	1.400	1.83	0.053	0.003	1.00
SWS	no identification	11	1.250	NA	0.185	NA	NA
DIA	rank = 1	118	0.735	1.07×10^{-16}	0.698	1	1.76×10^{-34}
DIA	rank = 2-5	66	1.257	0.700	0.255	0.617	5.70×10^{-3}
DIA	rank > 5	68	0.957	0.783	0.411	0.616	0.269
DIA	incorrect	70	1.550	1.30	0.143	0.304	0.533
DIA	no identification	81	1.050	NA	0.525	NA	NA

Figure S5. Histogram of SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID scores for incorrectly identified rank 1 structures and correctly identified structures independent of the rank. All standards in influent and effluent samples spiked at three concentration levels were considered.

Figure S6. The correlation between SMILES based priority score compared to a) area, b) LC_{50} and c) $\log I/E$ predicted based on SMILES with R^2 values of 0.07, 0.20 and 0.13, respectively. The comparison was done based on predicted values from SMILES and for integrated areas from pure solvent measurements. All variables were weakly correlated to the priority score (R^2 between 0.07 and 0.20; Figure 4) and the analysis of variance of log-scale linear model showed statistically significant contribution of each variable (p -value $< 2 \times 10^{-16}$ for all three variables) with LC_{50} accounting for largest share of explained variance (sum of squares of 15, 45, and 138, for area, $\log I/E$ and LC_{50} , respectively). This indicates that this approach is able to account for factors beyond peak area. For example, the highest priority among chemicals in the standard solution was assigned to ethyl azinphos ranked as 59th out of 90 chemicals by signal intensity, while the highest signal intensity was detected for tripropylamine ranked 68th based on priority score. This trend aligned with the risk quotients using the available experimental LC_{50} data – ethyl azinphos was ranked as highest priority standard based on its risk quotient (RQ = 19.0 rainbow trout, RQ = 231.4 bluegill) while tripropylamine was ranked 24th out of 32 standards with available LC_{50} data (RQ = 1.77*10⁻² fathead minnow).

Figure S7. Risk quotient comparison with predicted fingerprints-based priority score. The defined precautionary threshold of -3.52 is marked with an orange horizontal line. Accuracy (Acc), recall (Rec), and precision (Prec) were calculated based on classification using $RQ = 1$ and $PS_{RQ=1} = -1.53$. Number of unique chemicals N , correlation coefficient ρ , and p -value from Spearman test are shown on all subplots.

Table S10. WWTP1 samples overview. Total nr of peaks (IN and EF) = 13,133

	WWTP1					
	Influent			Effluent		
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	11,092 3,231 only in IN			9,902 2,041 only in EF (15%)		
	7,861 common (60%)					
	Persistent		Removable		Transformation products	
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	3,601 (27%)		6,352 (48%)		3,180 (24%)	
Out of which MS ² data acquired by at least one method	1,555		3,500		785	
Features with predicted fingerprints	1,354		2,973		615	
	Top5	SWS	DIA	Top5	SWS	DIA
Nr of detected peaks matched with full scan	3874	4211	4320	1424	1585	2324
Nr of MS ² triggered	2231	192	4302	707	160	2313
Nr of FP predicted	1802	156	3497	511	109	1891
Nr of peaks with any structural assignment (SIRIUS)	1396	141	2316	428	97	1353

Table S11. WWTP2 samples overview. Total nr of peaks (IN and EF) = 15,923

	WWTP2					
	Influent			Effluent		
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	14,730 2,412 only in IN			13,511 1,193 only in EF (7.5%)		
	12,318 common (77%)					
	Persistent		Removable		Transformation products	
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	6,543 (41%)		7,785 (49%)		1,595 (10%)	
Out of which MS ² data acquired by at least one method	3,509		4,275		344	
Features with predicted fingerprints	3,017		3,453		259	
	Top5	SWS	DIA	Top5	SWS	DIA
Nr of detected peaks matched with full scan	5056	5589	6436	2890	3329	4705
Nr of MS ² triggered	2553	213	6418	1461	187	4692
Nr of FP predicted	2051	157	5060	1094	146	3815
Nr of peaks with any structural assignment (SIRIUS)	1606	149	3010	873	131	2385

Table S12. WWTP3 samples overview. Total nr of peaks (IN and EF) = 9,751

	WWTP3					
	Influent			Effluent		
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	8,597 3,325 only in IN			6,426 1,154 only in EF (12%)		
	5,272 common (54%)					
	Persistent		Removable		Transformation products	
Nr of peaks detected in full scan (after blank subtraction)	2,615 (27%)		5,261 (54%)		1,875 (19%)	
Out of which MS ² data acquired by at least one method	1,153		3,037		641	
Features with predicted fingerprints	1,005		2,609		551	
	Top5	SWS	DIA	Top5	SWS	DIA
Nr of detected peaks matched with full scan	3371	3625	3551	1434	1526	1803
Nr of MS ² triggered	2184	183	3531	702	143	1793
Nr of FP predicted	1759	151	2884	481	98	1526
Nr of peaks with any structural assignment (SIRIUS)	1363	144	2061	404	91	1173

Figure S8. Overview of WWTP1 processing results

Figure S9. Overview of WWTP3 processing results

Figure S10. The FP-based PS and library-matched candidate structures correlation for WWTP2 features with $PS > PS_{RQ=1}$. All three features with a library match from effluent or aligned influent sample were detected with both Top5 and DIA data acquisition method.

Table S15. Summary of features (N=29) with predicted high risk in WWTP2 effluent. For majority of the features, a probable candidate structure on level 2 could not be assigned. Many detected chemicals elute close to dead time which complicates their analysis.

ID	Retention time (min)	Average m/z	Feature category	MS-DIAL manual peak shape investigation (1 – gaussian peak, 2 – overlapping features, 3 – unlikely to be a true feature)	Library match (GNPS)	Triggered by method	SIRIUS nr of candidates; Out of which in PubChemLite	MetFrag nr of candidates; Out of which in PubChemLite	Common in Top10 of SIRIUS and MetFrag	Comment
432	1.23	116.986	removable	2		DIA	NA	4 / 0	0	Slight area pattern similar to spiked chemicals – degradation of spiked chemical?
852	1.151	131.0017	removable	2		DIA Top5	9 / 9 NA	7 / 0 2 / 0	0	Low quality of the MS ² spectra
1254	1.161	143.019	removable	2		DIA Top5	NA NA	NA 6 / 1	0	No Na adducts
1996	1.173	161.001	persistent	3		DIA	NA	10 / 0	0	Feature present in blank and Dill only
2037	1.159	162.0304	persistent	2		DIA Top5	NA NA	10 / 0 10 / 5	0	
2223	1.707	167.0793	persistent	1		DIA Top5	2 / 2 NA	10 / 1 NA	0	
2542	1.134	175.0453	persistent	1		DIA Top5	3 / 1 NA	10 / 1 10 / 0	0	
2640	6.134	177.1124	removable	1		DIA Top5	10 / 2 10 / 5	10 / 1 10 / 0	0	Potential surfactant; also forms Na adduct.
3245	1.167	191.023	removable	2		DIA Top5	NA NA	7 / 0 10 / 0	0	
3325	1.136	193.0561	persistent	2		DIA	NA	10 / 0	0	
3421	4.325	195.088	removable	1		DIA Top5 SWS	10 / 4 10 / 4 10 / 4	10 / 0 10 / 0 10 / 0	0	Massbank suggests Caffeine, SIRIUS cannot explain m/z 152.98 in none of the top10 formulas (not feasible candidate based on elements?). No library match with GNPS. Standard in wastewater did not have that fragment
3858	1.137	203.0403	persistent	2		DIA Top5	NA NA	10 / 1 10 / 0	0	
4108	1.16	209.0335	persistent	2	3-[(1-Carboxy-vinyl)oxy]-benzoic acid	DIA Top5	NA NA	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	3-[(1-Carboxy-vinyl)oxy]-benzoic acid (GNPS). Structure-based PS of library match agrees with fingerprint-based PS; chemical is also in NORMAN SLE.

										MetFrag candidates are unlikely (No Cl pattern or neg mass balance)
4485	1.113	217.0387	persistent	2		DIA Top5	NA 8 / 7	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	SIRIUS Top2 for example Nithiazide (veterinary med) but identification scores low
4570	1.157	219.0178	removable	2 (No Cl pattern)		DIA Top5	4 / 4 4 / 4	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	SIRIUS top10 suggestions align well with candidate structure-based PS predictions
5967	1.18	250.931	transformation product	2		DIA	NA	10 / 1	0	
7565	2.12	284.0992	removable	1	(Guanosine suggested by aligned influent sample)	DIA Top5	10 / 4 NA	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	Guanosine (GNPS + SIRIUS). SIRIUS top1 suggestion aligns with a library match for MS ² spectrum from aligned influent feature
8509	8.879	301.165	persistent	1		DIA	10 / 2	10 / 0	0	SIRIUS top3 suggests Tripropylene glycol diacrylate (UV-cured inks and resins for dentistry and artificial nails; also in PubChemLite)
8727	9.874	305.1748	persistent	1		DIA Top5	10 / 3 10 / 2	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	SIRIUS top10 matches contain Tricyclodecanedimethanol diacrylate (Photosensitive agent)
9032	8.302	311.1472	persistent	1		DIA Top5	4 / 2 1 / 1	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	Rather low identification scores
9690	8.747	323.1472	persistent	1 (MS-DIAL suggests [M+Na] ⁺)		DIA Top5	6 / 4 6 / 4	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	SIRIUS suggest some adenosin-based structures (derivates) with low PS
10240	11.499	333.152	removable	1		DIA Top5	3 / 0 3 / 0	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	
11163	1.21	350.869	transformation product	2		DIA	2 / 1	10 / 0	0	Negative mass balance - could be halogenated
11513	10.793	357.2792	removable	1	Chenodeoxycholic Acid	DIA Top5	10 / 2 10 / 2	10 / 1 10 / 0	1	Chenodeoxycholic Acid (GNPS). SIRIUS suggests steroidal chemical. MetFrag a long non-saturated chain
12668	6.47	379.2497	persistent	1		DIA Top5	10 / 0 10 / 0	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	SIRIUS suggests ent-kaurane terpenoids (isomers)
13525	8.759	399.0554	persistent	1		DIA Top5	2 / 0 2 / 0	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	
13598	8.753	401.0518	persistent	1		DIA Top5	NA 1 / 0	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	
14741	7.899	429.0886	persistent	1		DIA Top5	1 / 1 NA	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	
17159	4.298	495.1493	persistent	1		DIA Top5	10 / 1 NA	10 / 0 10 / 0	0	

Table S16. Standards used for level 1 confirmation of the structure in WWTP3.

Standard			WWTP3				MS ² – standard (below x-axis) vs WW features (above x-axis); spectrum from IN	comment
Chemical	Exact mass m/z	RT	RT (IN)	RT (EF)	FP-based PS predicted in EF	MS ² from		
Caffeine	195.088201	2.90 3.68	3.66	3.67	-3.76 (-0.28 in IN)	IN		Categorized as removable
Paraxanthine	181.072551	3.18	2.02, 2.93, 3.18	2.01, 2.94, 3.19	-3.392 (-1.97 in IN)	IN		Categorized as removable. GNPS library matching suggests theobromine. Potentially present together with theobromine and/or theophylline
Hypoxanthine	137.04633 6	1.74-2.21	1.90-2.4	1.78-2.31	NA (-1.62 in IN)	IN		Categorized as removable. GNPS library matching also suggests hypoxanthine.
Guanine	152.05723	1.76	2.01, 2.25	1.86, 2.23	NA (-2.39 in IN)	IN, EF		Categorized as removable. Retention time of guanine does not align with detected feature. GNPS library matching suggests guanine.
Acetaminophen	152.07115	3.05	3.05	1.68, 1.71, 2.04, 2.20	NA (-2.07 in IN)	IN, EF		Categorized as removable.
Tetradecylamine	214.25347	6.78	6.40- 6.62	6.52?	-3.87 (-1.81 in IN)	IN		Categorized as removable. Retention time and MS ² spectra of tetradecylamine do not align with the detected feature

Figure S11. U-MAP fitted on PubChemLite (PCL) chemicals with A) spiked standards, *MS2Quant*, and *MS2Tox* training chemicals. Influent and effluent features together with features of $PS_{\text{precautionary}}$ and $PS_{RQ=1}$ are plotted for B) Top5, C) SWS, and D) DIA data acquisition methods. The applied models and detected features were visualized based on U-MAP embedding trained on PubChemLite (PCL) chemicals by Hupatz and Rahu et al.⁹ The visual investigation suggested that the chemical space of detected features is sufficiently covered by *MS2Quant* and *MS2Tox*, and the spread of chemicals used in this work for evaluating PS indicated good chemical variation. The influent and effluent features detected by Top5 and SWS data acquisition methods mapped on U-MAP were in relative proximity to the training set chemicals of the two models. The features detected with DIA seemingly cover the widest chemical space and had a wider spread compared to the spiked standards and chemicals used in the training of *MS2Quant* and *MS2Tox*. On the other hand, the fingerprint-based priority scores for spiked standards had highest variation for DIA measurements, indicating lower reliability of the predicted fingerprints. Thus, the wider chemical space coverage suggested for the DIA method should be further examined and validated. Both Top5 and DIA highlighted features over $PS_{RQ=1}$, which seem to generally belong to similar regions on the U-MAP. Similarly, the precautionary features from all data acquisition methods seem to overlap in the U-MAP chemical space. All in all, the visualizations indicate the complementarity of acquisition methods while suggesting that they also largely agree on the prioritized chemical subspace.

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